

A proposed conception of the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the age "Analytical study"

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Abstract. *The current study aims to identify the role of educational media in consolidating principles, values and societal security in light of the changing challenges of the era, to get out of them with a proposed vision that supports sound educational media and enhances peace, security and tranquility and rejects all forms of violence, hatred, extremism and fanaticism in creative and innovative ways and achieves the hope of broadcasting positive messages through the means Digital media that contribute to improvement, development, change, solving current problems and crises, supporting scientific research and investing it in rational decision-making, by analyzing and reviewing previous research and studies and educational literature that dealt with educational media and its role in facing current crises and challenges in a way that ensures an integrated therapeutic vision to confront contemporary challenges. The current study will differ from previous studies in the methodology of the study, as the current study depends on the analysis of educational literature through the descriptive analytical and developmental approach and in light of the results of previous studies. The study provides a set of recommendations.*

Keywords: *(educational media, challenges of the times).*

1. Introduction:

The media is a major dimension and a distinctive feature of the twenty-first century, as it is one of the pillars of the strategy for building development projects for all societies and in all fields, especially the educational field, due to the pivotal and essential role of educational institutions in the upbringing of students and the preparation of future generations. Economic, scientific, technological, and social development has become necessary; To enable generations to change, adapt and adapt to contemporary developments.

The media has an educational role in shaping the attitudes and trends of students and building the influential media personality and investing it as a tool for change in the educational process. different and to varying degrees.

In light of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the accelerating digital explosion, media education has become an urgent need. As a result of the digital transformation and the great demand for the Internet and its applications, as students accept to learn and expand media materials to express their opinions, ideas and themselves through Internet sites, especially social networking sites, they interact with cultural and political currents within cultural and media spaces, which requires educational institutions to keep pace with these developments and direct the media. To serve and achieve educational goals by investing technology and contemporary media and its techniques within the basic educational activities to achieve the desired goals and objectives, integrate students into their societies,

and refine the personality of a good citizen who is integrated into his society, disciplined by our laws, morals and values, and open to the world.

The study Problem

Hence, this study came to answer the main question of the study: What is the proposed perception of the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the age? The following sub-questions emerge from it:

- **What is the concept of educational media in light of the challenges of the times?**
- **What is the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the age?**
- **What is the proposed perception of the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the times?**

Study Significance

Scientific significance (theoretical):

- It is hoped that policy makers will benefit from this study by enacting laws and policies that enhance the role of educational media and instill its principles in educational institutions and society as a priority.
- It is hoped that the recommendations of this study will benefit the leaders to play their role in encouraging students and researchers to continuously evaluate and provide feedback on educational media.

The importance of the study from a theoretical and intellectual point of view:

- - It is hoped that this study will represent a scientific addition to its subject, which is an urgent need in our time and one of the literature that libraries need, according to the researchers' knowledge.
- It is hoped that this study will provide scientific and research horizons for other researchers to delve into such a field in order to bring about the desired development and add new knowledge to educational thought and scientific research to bring about the required positive change.

Study Methodology:

The study used the descriptive, analytical, developmental approach, as it used the theoretical approach with reference to the theoretical literature and studies related to the topic; To form a theory of specialized ideas and concepts in the field of study, and to review relevant previous studies, by analyzing the literature related to the study; To reach the answer to the study questions and to provide a number of recommendations.

Previous studies:

- **Ali, Abdel-Rahman and Hussein (2022)** conducted a study aimed at revealing the effectiveness of a proposed program in educational media based on infographics to provide students with hearing disabilities with media photography skills. The dependent variables, and the experimental research sample consisted of a group of students from Al-Amal School for the Deaf and Hard of Hearing in Minya, consisting of (26) individuals. It contains the nature of educational media, its branches, and the objectives of each branch. The school journalism branch and its branches have taken media photography skills and designed them in the form of lessons. Measurement tools were applied before and after learning, and the most important results concluded to the effectiveness of the proposed program based on infographics in the knowledge and skill achievement of media photography skills.

- Younes (2022) conducted a study aimed at identifying the use of mobile phone montage applications by students of educational media departments in the production of media materials, as in recent years the adoption of the mobile phone has increased rapidly all over the world, including developed and developing countries, and it has spread among many individuals in all parts of the world. Cultural levels and social classes and its success among young people, and thus it is characterized by being the fastest spreading modern technology among individuals compared to the rest of the technological innovations that preceded it. To the development of systems for preparing and transmitting audio and video and increasing the capacity of data transmission and storage, which will make it easier to use the image, direct and recorded video more simply and easily. To carry out all the stages of producing the photographed work (preparation - filming - editing - directing). Smart mobile phones offer many free and non-free editing applications, in order to make it easier for students and journalists in their work of producing various videos and storyboards.

- **Doabeh (2022)** conducted a study aimed at identifying the effect of a training program based on educational scaffolding in developing media literacy skills for students of educational media: a quasi-experimental study. The aim of the current research is to study the educational scaffolding theory as one of the pioneering modern educational strategies and educational theories in developing the educational and educational process, and to try to explore the extent of its effectiveness in achieving media learning and developing media education skills for students. A training based on educational scaffolding in developing media education skills for students of educational media? The research relied on the quasi-experimental approach, and the research tools were represented in the two scales of media education skills and assessment of educational scaffolding theory from the students' point of view, and they were applied to an experimental sample of educational media students consisting of (40) students, and the results concluded that there are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of The students in the two applications, the pre and post applications regarding media education skills as a whole, in favor of the post application, where the values of (T) were a function at the significance level of 0.001, and there was a medium direct relationship between the students' scores with regard to media education skills and their scores on the educational scaffolding theory assessment scale, where it was ($0,3 > t > 0,7$), which is a function at the 0.01 level, and there are statistically significant differences between the mean scores of students in the dimensional application and the sequential application on the scale of media education skills in favor of the sequential application, where the values of (T) are significant at the significance level of 0.001.

- **Al-Ghafiri and Al-Qahtani (2022)** conducted a study aimed at identifying the contribution of educational media to providing primary school students with dimensions of social responsibility from the teachers' point of view. It relied on the descriptive survey method, and the study population consisted of all female primary school teachers in Abha, who numbered (1817) female teachers, and the total sample total was (808) female teachers. Social responsibility (personal, religious, moral, national, towards the environment), from (36) phrases. The results of the study showed that the degree of educational media's contribution to providing primary school students with dimensions of social responsibility from the teachers' point of view is large with an arithmetic mean (4.05), and the order of the questionnaire axes according to the degree of educational media contribution in descending order is as follows: The patriotism is very large with an arithmetic average (4.20), the degree of educational media's contribution to giving primary school students responsibility towards the environment is great at an arithmetic average (4.06), the degree of educational media's contribution to giving primary school students great personal responsibility in an arithmetic medium (3.99), the degree of educational media's contribution In giving primary school students a great moral responsibility with an arithmetic

mean of (3.96), the study also showed that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance of 0.05 in the degree of educational media's contribution to giving primary school students the dimensions of social responsibility according to the educational qualification towards the recipients of (diploma), There are also statistically significant differences at the significance level of 0.05 in the degree of educational media's contribution to the acquisition of primary school students dimensions Social responsibility according to participation in educational media activities towards (participation in educational media programs and activities).

- **Younes (2022)** conducted a study aimed at identifying the role that social media (Facebook) can play as an alternative means for school journalism, used by the educational media specialist during crises and disasters. To inform teachers and students of the most important instructions that the school administration or mentors seek to convey to them, and also sought to know the role they can play as guiding means for students; To search for sites that benefit them in the educational process during the beginning of the Corona pandemic, and how it is developing, through an analytical research on a sample of the pages of some schools on Facebook, they are schools: (Safia Zaghoul Secondary School for Girls affiliated to the Al-Qubba Gardens Educational Department - Al-Salam Preparatory School for Benin, affiliated to the Waili administration Educational - Al-Qubba Al-Fedawiya Primary School affiliated to Al-Waili Educational Administration), from December 2018 until November 2021, and the researcher used a content analysis form for the school pages of the research sample. A complementary relationship, which can never cancel each other out; Rather, they work side by side during times of crises and disasters - God forbid - and to achieve the idea of the present and the present. Then the most important recommendations of the research came to the necessity of conducting some related research.

- **Abd al-Rahman, Ahmad and Hindawi (2022)** conducted a study that aimed to study and analyze the relationship between the roles of educational media and the dissemination of intellectual security among secondary school students. Governmental schools and (100) private schools. The research tools were a survey form for high school students. The results indicated that there is a direct, statistically significant, correlation between the rate of secondary school students' dependence on educational media and the degree of their knowledge of intellectual security. And there is a direct, statistically significant, correlation between the rate of secondary school students' dependence on educational media and their level of intellectual security. And the absence of a statistically significant correlation between the motives of the study sample's dependence on educational media and the degree of their knowledge of intellectual security. And the existence of a direct, statistically significant, correlation between the rate of dependence on educational media in schools, the sample of the study, and the effects resulting from that dependence. And there are statistically significant differences between secondary school students, the study sample, in their grade averages on the scale of media influences resulting from reliance on educational media according to demographic variables (gender, place of residence, economic level of the family), and there are statistically significant differences between secondary school students in the study sample. In their average score on the Intellectual Security Scale according to demographic variables (gender, place of residence, family economic level).

- **Juma and Al-Sayed (2022)** conducted a study aimed at identifying the role of educational media in confronting the phenomenon of intellectual extremism, and to achieve this purpose, the research contained a framework that included (identifying the ethics of educational media and the professional principles of these ethics, and clarifying the importance of the ethical aspect in media practice to ensure the quality of media work And a presentation of the concept of educational media, the concept of belonging and the factors affecting it, trying to reach the role that educational media

plays in confronting intellectual extremism, identifying the obstacles that prevent this and the requirements for activating educational media in promoting correct thought, and a presentation of some of the features and characteristics of educational media activities (their objectives, and their basics). And its contents) and the methods and methods of presenting educational media, then it dealt with some educational media activities and their role in confronting the phenomenon of intellectual extremism. The research mechanism includes results and suggestions, as the researcher was able to come up with suggestions to strengthen the role of educational media in confronting intellectual extremism.

Commenting on previous studies:

The current study agrees with the study of Jumaa and Al-Sayed (2022), Abdulrahman, Ahmed, and Hindawi (2022), Younis (2022), Al-Ghafiri and Al-Qahtani (2022), Duaba (2022) and Younes (2022) in the role of educational media in guiding and building students' ideas and refining a healthy personality belonging to their homeland Love for its members and proud of its culture, values, customs and traditions through the establishment of effective dialogue and constructive mobility and acceptance of the other opinion and renounce fanaticism and intellectual extremism and the need to direct influencers on social networking sites and in the media to serve the community through educational media guidance.

Conclusion:

To answer the first question of the study: "What is the concept of educational media in light of the challenges of the age?"

The educational media cannot be separated from the educational process. Rather, it is an integral part of it. It has a functional, directive, coordination, and evaluation relationship. It is one of the basic pillars for raising students to believe in abilities, express opinion, dialogue, debate, take appropriate decisions, respect the other opinion, interact with society and keep pace with development. Scientific, technical, and cognitive literature, and the educational and media literature was concerned with the necessity of integration between media and education. The educational goal must be within the strategic media plans. The need for educational media came as a reflection and reaction to contemporary educational strategies.

The educational media is any kind of media used to educate individuals about a subject at home or in educational institutions, and it is defined as the educational duties of the public media.). It is to highlight the educational role of radio, the press and theater in the educational and educational field with the aim of raising awareness, educating, educating and teaching (Al-Ghafiri and Al-Qahtani, 2022, 169). To make effective use of the information provided by the media (Ali, Hussein, 2022, 629).

To answer the second question of the study: What is the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the age?

The educational media is the optimal investment for the means of communication to achieve the goals efficiently and effectively in the light of the educational and media policies of the state. The researchers focused on the objectives of educational media, and the study summarized them as follows:

- Contributes to the achievement of educational policy objectives.
- Instilling moral values and consolidating the principles of the moral system.

- Develop students' constructive behavioral attitudes and ideals in society.
- An active role in solving the problems of society, and raising awareness towards them to contribute to solving the problem and not part of it.
- Belonging and loyalty to the homeland and its children, institutions and facilities.
- Access to successful experiences, benefit from scientific visions, and actively participate in development and change.
- Encouraging and embracing scientific research and researchers and highlighting their expertise and experiences
- Adopting educational issues and problems and addressing them in the media
- Creating a positive, interactive, participatory relationship based on trust and respect for the opinion of others
- - Continuous communication in all directions between society, educational and media institutions to disseminate news with credibility and correct and accurate information from reliable sources and to reject rumors.

To answer the third question of the study: What is the proposed perception of the role of educational media in light of the challenges of the age?

The importance of educational media is highlighted by linking media and education with a fine line that needs to be drawn with great accuracy. The first media person in society is the teacher, as Al-Shazly Al-Fitouri confirms. It is no coincidence that the derivation of the vocabulary of information and education took place from one root, and thus the difference between information and education became apparent in terms of the intensity of the occurrence of the act, not in terms of its nature. The educational media has a large number of media such as text, image, video and audio. And its pivotal role is in educating students about the lifestyle and lifestyle and how to plan their goals and ideas so that they are not part of others' plans and how to be influential and not only affected, through positive messages in local media channels and ideas that are included in books, curricula or training courses, simulation, virtual reality, the Internet, its software and applications And investing it as a powerful way to blend tools, media, and education goals because most people have accounts on social media, they are familiar with how the platforms work, so pretty much everyone can help their district maintain a positive presence on social media. The study presents the proposed scenario

moral education	Have good manners and respect the teacher. spread love; Love of the homeland, love of parents, love of science, love of science and knowledge, and the consolidation of noble Islamic values, love for colleagues, loyalty and belonging to the homeland, maintaining order and adherence to its laws and policies.
social education	Take advantage of modern means of communication, and adapt them to serve the educational act. And the educational media is required to follow up the behavior of students within educational institutions and in society. The need to preserve the school in its building and its meaning
human education	To live with the temporal and spatial conditions of his society. Among the tasks that he must assure people are: the real concepts of education, and to eliminate the concept that links education to

	employment, and the desire for prominent jobs that some call high or high.. We want children to learn how the labor force is an honorable hand. Their love for God Almighty, and to realize that professions and crafts are better than unemployment and want, and that the country will not always depend on other than its children.
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Recommendations:

- The necessity of focusing on the importance of educational media in relation to the educational process in order to confront the challenges of the times
- Adoption of the proposed vision from the Ministry of Higher Education.

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